

QNFO Innovations: US Patents Pending

19/043,486	Bio-Inspired Platform for Enhanced Quantum Coherence
19/043,521	Liquid Shielded Quantum Device
19/088,934	System and Method for Probabilistic Quantum Information Processing via Information States
19/171,267	Phase-Encoded Information System for Unified Storage and Processing
63/751,846	Quantum Processing Unit with Bio-Inspired Lattice Structure for Enhanced Qubit Coherence and Scalability
63/751,887	Bio-Inspired Platform for Enhanced Quantum Coherence
63/766,414	Analog Quantum Observation and Simulation System Using Non-Collapsing Probabilistic States
63/772,770	Analog Quantum Observation and Simulation System Using Non-Collapsing Probabilistic States
63/780,399	Analog Quantum Observation and Simulation System Using Non-Collapsing Probabilistic States
63/784,100	Phase-Encoded Information System for Unified Storage and Processing
63/824,935	Integrated Nanoscale Quantum Shield for Enhanced Coherent Operation at Elevated Temperatures
63/837,236	Resonant Field Computing System and Method Using Engineered Field State Qubits
63/840,123	Harmonic Resonance Computing System and Method Using Delocalized Resonant Field State Computational Units; and Resonant Field Computing System and Method Using Engineered Field State Qubits
63/842,205	Harmonic Resonance Computing System and Method Utilizing Telecommunications Network Infrastructure; and System and Method for Harmonic Resonance Computing Leveraging Intrinsic Network Dynamics
63/842,356	Harmonic Resonance Computing System and Method Utilizing an Engineered Three-Dimensional Toroidal Physical Medium Supporting Predictable Semi-Harmonic Energy States and Computationally Exploited Unstable Nodes
63/843,145	Harmonic Resonance Computing System and Method; and Method Leveraging Universal Resonant Principles and Wave Phenomena for Information Processing and Artificial Intelligence; and Method Utilizing Engineered Physical Media and Network Dynamics
63/846,855	Various Systems and Methods Related to Computing
63/847,035	Various Systems and Methods for Computing v20250719-2
63/852,206	WAVE-BASED COMPUTATIONAL SYSTEMS AND SIMULATORS THEREOF